

Imaging of Primary Neuroendocrine Breast Carcinoma About Three Clinical Cases and Review of the Literature

Authors:

Radia Benyahia¹, Fadwa. Hocine¹, Oulad Said Nabila¹, Mohamed Ali Abdellaoui¹, Esma Kerboua², Souhila Aziez², Salah Eddine. Bendib¹.

¹Medical imaging department, Pierre and Marie Curie Center, University of Algiers 1, Algeria.

²Medical Oncology Department, CPMC, University of Algiers 1, Algeria.

¹Pierre and Marie Curie Center, University of Algiers 1, Algeria.

Corresponding Author:

Radia Benyahia

University of Algiers 1, Faculty of Medicine, Algiers1 University Hospital Center, Pierre and Marie Curie. Mustapha Hospital Radiology and medical imaging department, Algiers Algeria

Article Received: 21-October-2021, Revised: 11-November-2021, Accepted: 01-December-2021

ABSTRACT:

The article reports three cases of primary breast neuroendocrine tumor, which is a rare form of breast cancer, derived from neuroendocrine cells. The three patients, aged 53, 51 and 47 years respectively, had no family or personal history of breast and ovarian cancer. Imaging showed variable appearances: the first case was an irregular mass, without microcalcifications and the second case the mass was lobulated, with microcalcifications having 18F-FDG uptake. The third was irregular in shape and contours. The diagnosis was confirmed by biopsy, which revealed the expression of neuroendocrine markers such as chromogranin A and synaptophysin. The patients were treated with surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, with regular follow-up. The article discusses the radiological, epidemiological, clinical, histological and therapeutic characteristics of this rare entity, based on a review of the literature,

Keywords: Neuroendocrine carcinoma, breast, mammography, ultrasound, biopsy, immunohistochemistry. MRI.

INTRODUCTION:

Neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) are rare tumors, derived from neuroendocrine cells, capable of synthesizing and secreting hormones or peptides. They can develop in different organs, including the pancreas, digestive tract, lung, ovary and thymus. The breast is a very unusual site for NETs, accounting for less than 1% of all breast tumors 1. Imaging plays an important role in the screening, diagnosis, staging and monitoring of breast NETs. The most commonly used imaging modalities are mammography, ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and positron emission tomography coupled to CT (PET-CT). The

objective of this article is to present the imaging aspects of a case of large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast, which is the rarest and most aggressive type of breast NET.

Observation: 1

This is a 52-year-old patient, postmenopausal for 2 years, with no personal or family history of breast cancer, who underwent a screening mammogram, revealing a high-density, lobulated left breast mass, with irregular contours, homogeneous, without microcalcifications within it, sit at the level of the left QSE (figure 1).

Figure 1. Frontal (a) and oblique (b) mammographic image showing the presence in the upper outer quadrants of the left breast, of irregular contours of irregular shape without microcalcifications within it; lesion classified BI-RADS 4 of the ACR.

Additional ultrasound revealed a lobulated, hypoechoic, homogeneous mass with irregular contours affecting the left upper outer quadrant measuring 9.5 mm, as well as suspicious ipsilateral axillary lymphadenopathy (figure 2).

Figure 2. Ultrasound appearance showing a tau mass in the upper outer quadrant of the left breast with irregular shape and contours, hypoechoic, heterogeneous classified lesion classified BI-RADS 4 of the ACR.

The radiological file was classified BI-RADS 4c of the ACR. The clinical examination was classified as T1cN1M0. A microbiopsy taken under ultrasound control came back in favor of a breast neuroendocrine tumor. A thoraco-abdominopelvic scan, requested as part of a remote extension assessment, came back negative.

A breast MRI carried out as part of an extension assessment looking for multi-focality, multi-centricity, bilaterality but also looking for damage to the pectoral muscle since the lesion was deep in intimate contact with the pectoral muscle, showed a mass of irregular shape, with spiculated contours, in T1, intermediate T2 hyposignal, with intense and heterogeneous contrast enhancement in the arterial phase, and persistent contrast enhancement in the late phase, producing a type 3 hemodynamic curve, measuring 14.5x8.6 mm, located in the upper outer quadrant of the left breast. This mass did not show signs of tumor extension (Fig. 3). There was also left axillary lymphadenopathy, Berg I, with intermediate signal on T1, high signal on T2, with intense and homogeneous contrast enhancement.

Figure 3. MRI appearance T1 sequence (a), sequence with injection of contrast product (b), subtraction sequence (c) showing a mass in the upper outer quadrant of the left breast with an irregular shape and contours, in hyposignal T1, enhancing heterogeneously after injection of contrast product producing a type 3 hemodynamic curve classified lesion classified BI-RADS 5 of the ACR.

The decision of the multidisciplinary consultation meeting was to perform a lumpectomy. The patient had undergone a lumpectomy, referred to the oncologist for neoadjuvant chemotherapy, followed by breast-conserving surgery and radiotherapy. Adjuvant hormonal treatment is also considered. The surgical specimen came back in favor of a primary neuroendocrine carcinoma tumor of the invasive left breast, presenting a ductal component in situ strongly expressing the neuroendocrine marker synaptophysin, as well as the hormonal receptors (ER 80%, RP 70%), but not the receptor HER2. Ki-67 is high at 35%. The lymph node dissection was negative. The diagnosis of neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast was thus made.

figure 4. Tumor proliferation with neuroendocrine architecture (a). Intense immuno-expression of synaptophysin (b) and Chomogranin A (c).

Observation: 2

This is a 47-year-old patient, with no personal or family history of breast or ovarian cancer, followed for hypothyroidism who underwent a diagnostic mammogram, following bilateral mastodynia, evolving for 6 months. The mammogram revealed a high-density left breast mass, lobulated in shape, with irregular contours, heterogeneous, containing polymorphic calcifications within it, located at the level of the left QSE (figure 1).

Figure 1. Frontal mammographic image (a) and enlargement image (b) showing the presence in the external quadrant of the left breast, of a mass with irregular contours of a lobulated shape containing microcalcifications within it; lesion classified BI-RADS 4 of the ACR.

An additional ultrasound revealed a mass affecting the left upper outer quadrant, measuring 27x12 mm with a lobulated shape, with irregular contours, hypoechoic, heterogeneous by the presence of echogenic spots within it related to calcifications. This mass has irregular contours, including two ipsilateral axillary lymphadenopathy, containing suspicious micro calcifications, the largest of which measured 20x17mm (figure 2).

Figure 2. Ultrasound appearance showing a tau mass in the upper outer quadrant of the left breast with an irregular shape and contours, hypoechoic, heterogeneous containing echogenic spots related to microcalcifications suggestive of suspicious left breast mass (a), associated with lymphadenopathy. thick cortex, containing echogenic spots whose fatty center is eccentric (b).

The radiological file was classified BI-RADS 4b by the ACR. The clinical examination was classified as T2N1M0. A microbiopsy taken under ultrasound guidance came back in favor of an infiltrating ductal carcinoma and the cytopuncture of the lymphadenopathy was metastatic in nature.

A thoraco-abdominal-pelvic scan, requested as part of a remote extension assessment, was negative.

The decision of the multidisciplinary consultation meeting was to perform a mastectomy with lymph node dissection followed by adjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy.

The patient had undergone a mastectomy and lymph node dissection. The surgical specimen came back in favor of an invasive left breast infiltrating ductal carcinoma, with an intraductal contingent in situ, of central necrosis. Hormonal receptors (ER 70%, RP 0%), but not the HER2 receptor. The lymph node dissection was positive.

The patient received adjuvant treatment in 6 courses, followed by radiotherapy.

One year after the end of treatment, the patient presented with abdominal pain syndrome of the right hypochondrium. An abdominal ultrasound carried out as part of the emergency, found multiple nodular, hyperechoic, hyper vascularized lesions, confirmed on liver MRI suggesting secondary localizations but rarely observed in the context of a breast primary, from which a liver biopsy was performed, revealing liver metastases of a neuroendocrine carcinoma since the

tumor cells strongly expressed Homogranin A and Synaptophysin on immunohistochemistry. Serum chromogranin A was, however, found at concentrations higher than normal with a rate of A PET-CT with 18 FDG carried out in search of the primary focus was negative.

The rereading of the anatomopathological blocks and the immunohistochemical study found positive marking for Chomogranin A and Synaptophysin, confirming the neuroendocrine nature of the breast lesions,

The patient benefited from adjuvant chemotherapy in relation to the neuroendocrine nature of the lesion. The hepatic therapeutic response was very favorable with disappearance of the lesions.

Observation 3:

This is a 53-year-old patient, with no personal or family history of breast or ovarian cancer, followed for arterial hypertension who underwent a mammogram following self-palpation of a recent appearance of a right breast mass, then a year ago the mammogram was normal (figure 1a, 1b). The new mammogram revealed a high-density right breast mass, irregular in shape, with irregular contours, homogeneous, located in the retro-areolar region measuring 23mm associated with a second mass with the same morphological aspects as the original mass measuring 11mm (figure 1).

Figure 1. Mammographic images of the faces (a, b) were normal and mammographic images of the faces (c, d) and external obliques showing the presence in the right retro areolar of two masses of homogeneous irregular contours and shapes without microcalcifications within it; lesion classified BI-RADS 4c of the ACR.

An additional ultrasound examination revealed two contiguous masses in the right retro-areolar regions of irregular shape and contours, hypoechoic, heterogeneous, attenuating in places measuring 24 mm and 10 mm, 11 mm apart, as well as two ipsilateral axillary lymphadenopathies, 8 and 10 mm apart. 9mm (figure 2).

Figure 2. Ultrasound appearance showing two contiguous masses at the level of right retro-areolar regions of irregular shape and contours, hypoechoic, heterogeneous, attenuating in places evoking suspicious right breast mass (a,b), associated with lymphadenopathy with thick cortex, containing echogenic spots whose fatty center is eccentric (c)

The radiological file was classified BI-RADS 5 from the ACR. The clinical examination was classified as cT2N1M0. A microbiopsy of the two masses, carried out under ultrasound guidance, came back in favor of an infiltrating ductal carcinoma and the cytopuncture of the lymphadenopathy was metastatic in nature. The patient underwent a breast MRI as part of an extension assessment which revealed a multi-focal, multi-centric right breast tumor process.

Figure 3. MRI appearance T1 sequence (a), sequence with injection of MIP contrast product (b), subtraction sequence (c) and dynamic curve (d) showing several masses at the level of the right retro-areolar region of shapes and sizes. irregular contours, T1 hyposignal, enhancing heterogeneously after injection of contrast product producing a type 3 hemodynamic curve classified BI-RADS 6 of the ACR.

A thoraco-abdominal-pelvic scan, requested as part of a remote extension assessment, was negative. The decision of the multidisciplinary consultation meeting was to perform a mastectomy with lymph node dissection followed by adjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy. The patient had undergone a mastectomy and lymph node dissection. The surgical specimen came back in favor of a grade III carcinomatous process, poorly differentiated into clusters and large lobules and with basophilic cells. Hormone receptors (ER 80%, RP 60%), but not the HER2 and KI67 receptor at 65%. The lymph node dissection was positive (figure 4). the immunohistochemical study also found positive marking for Chomogranin A and Synaptophysin, confirming the neuroendocrine nature of the breast lesions.

figure 4. Tumor proliferation with neuroendocrine architecture (a). Intense immuno-expression of synaptophysin (b) and Chromogranin A (c).

The patient received adjuvant treatment in 6 courses, followed by radiotherapy.

DISCUSSION:

Breast neuroendocrine carcinomas are rare, accounting for less than 0.1% of all breast cancers and less than 1% of neuroendocrine tumors [1]. They have been described in other organs such as the thymus (2), stomach (3), cervix (4), colon and rectum (3), urinary tract (5), ovary (6), the ampulla of Vater (7), the salivary glands and the uterine body (8). Mainly affecting women, between the 6th and 7th decade (9, 10), but younger cases have been reported in the literature as is the case of our 52-year-old patient. The clinical appearance associates a non-specific lesion of often slow evolution, made up of a mass with or without axillary lymphadenopathy. The immuno-expression of neuroendocrine markers is present in more than 50% of the tumor volume [11].

Primary breast neuroendocrine tumor is a diagnosis of exclusion. The scanner eliminates the primary sites: lungs, ENT sphere, digestive, skin and this is the case of our patient [12, 13].

On mammography, neuroendocrine carcinoma most often presents as an irregular mass, with irregular contours, with a homogeneous density. It may or may not be associated with microcalcifications, which are generally coarse, pleomorphic or in clusters, suggestive of invasive carcinoma. Radiologically, stellar or speculative masses on mammography are rare [14]. The size of these tumors can reach up to 15 cm. The imaging is not specific and is similar to other histological types with malignant semiologies.

On ultrasound, neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast appears as a hypoechoic mass, with irregular or spiculated contours, with internal or peripheral vascularization. It often presents necrotic, hemorrhagic or cystic areas, or internal calcifications [15].

However, Günhan et al. [16] described that common radiological features of breast neuroendocrine tumors include a high-density mass with spiculated or lobulated margins on mammography, and often homogeneous, on ultrasound, without being able to formally differentiate them from ductal carcinomas.

On MRI, neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast appears as a mass with low signal on T1, intermediate signal on T2, with intense and heterogeneous contrast enhancement in the arterial and portal phase. It often shows persistent contrast enhancement in the late phase, related to tumor neoangiogenesis. MRI also makes it possible to assess tumor extension to the nipple, skin or pectoral muscle, as well as the presence of multifocal or bilateral lesions.

The clinical-radiological appearance therefore seems similar to infiltrating ductal carcinoma.

The definitive diagnosis is based on the anatomopathological study allowing certainty about

the breast origin, by highlighting an in situ contingent; and also by the immuno-expression of hormonal receptors by the tumor cells also supports the primitive nature. On the immunohistochemical study by the expression of a neuroendocrine marker by at least 50% of the tumor cells. Synaptophysin is the most sensitive and specific neuroendocrine marker [17].

Treatment of neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast is similar to that of nonspecific invasive carcinoma of the breast. It is based on surgery, which can be conservative or radical depending on the stage and tumor size, followed by radiotherapy. Neoadjuvant or adjuvant chemotherapy is often indicated, due to the high grade and high metastatic potential of these tumors.

CONCLUSION:

Primary neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast is exceptional. Its radiological appearance remains non-specific. Diagnostic certainty is provided by the anatomopathological and immunohistochemical study by expressing specific markers (chromogranin and synaptophysin). The treatment remains non-standardized but the place of surgery remains indisputable.

REFERENCES:

1. Trabelsi A, Benabdelkrim S, Stita W, Gharbi O, Jaidane L, Hmissa S, et al. Carcinome neuroendocrine primitif du sein. *Imagerie de la femme*. 2008;18(3):184–186. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[Ref list](#)]
- 2) Chetty R, Batitang S, Govender D. Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the thymus. *Histopathology* 1997;31:274–6.
- (3) *Gastroentérologie Clinique et Biologique* Volume 30, Issue 2, February 2006, Pages 276-291 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-8320\(06\)73165-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0399-8320(06)73165-7)
- (4) Soufiane Baggar, Hajar Ouahbi, Meryem Azegrar, et Al : Carcinome neuroendocrine du col utérin: à propos d'un cas avec revue de la littérature *Pan Afr Med J*. 2017; 27: 82. DOI : 10.11604/pamj.2017.27.82.10902
- (5) Hicham El Bote, Abelilah El Alaoui, Ziouani Oussama, et Al : Carcinome neuroendocrine de la

vessie: à propos de 5 cas Pan Afr Med J. 2017; 26: 92. DOI : 10.11604/pamj.2017.26.92.11488

(6) Pr S.Hadjaraba Hadjarabb Pr N.Djennane Bouzid Pr S.Mimounia : Association rare d'une tumeur endocrine ovarienne droite et d'un lymphome de l'ovaire gauche Annales d'Endocrinologie Volume 79, Issue 4, September 2018, Pages 455-456 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ando.2018.06.854>

(7) Cavazza A, Gallo M, Valcavi R, De Marco L, Gardini. Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater. Arch Pathol Lab Med 2003;127:221–3. www.ijcrt.org © 2021 IJCRT | Volume 9, Issue 3 March 2021 | ISSN: 2320-2882 IJCRT2103249 International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) www.ijcrt.org 1955

(8) Erhan Y, Dickmen Y, Yucebilgin MS, Zekioglu O, Mgoyi L, Terek MC. Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the uterine corpus metastatic to brain and lung: case report and review of the literature. Eur J Gynaecol Oncol 2004;25:109–12

(9) Tavassoli FA, Devilee P. Tumours of the breast. In: Tavassoli FA, Devilee P, eds. Pathology and genetics of tumours of the breast and female genital organs. World Health Organization Classification of Tumours Series. Lyon: IARC Press, 2003:32-34

(10) Eun Deok Chang, MD, Min Kyun Kim, MD, Jeong Soo Kim, MD, In Yong Whang, MD. Primary Neuroendocrine Tumor of the Breast: Imaging Features: Korean J Radiol 2013;14(3):395-399

11. Ellis IO, Schnitt SJ, Sastre-Garau X, et al. Tumours of the breast, neuroendocrine tumours. In: Tavassoli FA, Devilee P, editors. *World Health Organization Classification of tumours, Pathology and genetics of tumours of the breast and female genital organs*. Lyon: IARC; pp. 32–4. 200.

12. Scaramuzzi G, Murgio RM, Cuttitta A, Ciuffreda L. Neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast - Our experience and a proposal of a therapeutic algorithm for a rare tumor. *G Chir*. 2008 May;29(5):203–6.

13. Fujimoto Y, Yagyū R, Murase K, Kawajiri H, Ohtani H, Arimoto Y, et al. A case of solid neuroendocrine carcinoma of the breast in a 40-year-old. *Breast Cancer*. 2007;14(2):250–3.

14. Amiraslanov A, Muradov H, Veliyeva H. Breast endocrine cancer. *Georgian Med News*. 2009 Feb;(167):36–9.

15. Boufettal H, Noun M, Mahdaoui S, Hermas S, Samouh N. Une tumeur du sein inhabituelle: le carcinome endocrine mammaire primitif. *Imagerie de la Femme*. 2011;21(1):35–38.

(16) Günhan-Bilgen I, Zekioglu O, Ustün EE, Memis A, Erhan Y. Neuroendocrine differentiated breast carcinoma: imaging features correlated with clinical and histopathological findings. *Eur Radiol* 2003;13:788-793

(17) Moriya T, Kanomata N, Kozuka Y et al. Usefulness of immunohistochemistry for differential diagnosis between benign and malignant breast lesions. *Breast Cancer*. 2009; 16:173-178.